

Protocol: Production of Salkowski Reagent (From NaOH, FeCl₃, NH₄ClO₄, and HCl)

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Abstract

Salkowski reagent often used tool for quantifying the presence of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) among other indoles. It is a mixture of perchloric (HClO₄) at 35% concentration and ferric chloride (FeCl₃) at a 0.5M concentration (Gang, Sharma and Saraf). Salkowski reagent turns pink in the presence of IAA due to a reaction that forms an IAA complex with Fe³⁺ and its subsequent reduction (Kamnev, Shchelochkov and Perfiliev). Although one can order perchloric acid from various sources, costs or restrictions may prevent the direct order of perchloric acid. We developed this protocol to produce Salkowski reagent using readily available lab chemicals.

Protocol

Materials:

1. _____ 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask (Fisherbrand™ Catalog No. FB100250)
2. _____ Five (5) Stir Bar (Fisherbrand™ Catalog No.14-512-124)
3. _____ Laboratory Support Stand (XMWangzi Part No. US-Ind-A002)
4. _____ Burette, 100ml - Class A (Burrell MPN: 17027F-100)
5. _____ Burette, 25ml - Class A (Eisco Labs Part No. CH0240BWT)
6. _____ Three (3) plastic weight boats (Pure Ponta Part No. mdo-azoc-1030)
7. _____ Magnetic Stirrer (INTLLAB Model No. MS-500)
8. _____ Two (2) 50 ml media bottles (Sigma Aldrich SKU CLS139550-1EA)
9. _____ Hot plate (Thermo Scientific Cat Code HP88854100)
10. _____ Vacuum filtration flask (QingYi Part No. Suction Filter)
11. _____ Three (3) Lab Spoon Spatula (AOZITA Part No. D3-2P)
12. _____ PH Strips (Fisherbrand™ Hydrion™ Catalog No.14-850-125)
13. _____ 100 ml graduated cylinder (SEOH Part No. 54T11)
14. _____ 25 ml graduated cylinder (Ronyes Lifescience Part No. 452134)
15. _____ 150 ml beaker (Fisherbrand™ Catalog No. FB100150)
16. _____ Four (4) Glass funnels (stonylab Part No. Filter-Glass-1PK-All)
17. _____ Thermometer (SP Bel-Art Part No. B60800-3100)
18. _____ Three (3) 50 ml Erlenmeyer flasks (Modern Curiosity Part No. IERL-001-007-PARENT)
19. _____ Vortex Mixer (INTLLAB Part No. VM-370)
20. _____ Scale 0 – 500 g (Carolina® Item #: 702357)
21. _____ Pumice Boiling Stones (Carolina® Item #: 848280)

Reagents:

1. _____ HCl 36% (Carolina Biological Supply Co. Product No. 86-7790)

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2. _____ NaOH (Innovating Science Product No. IS 28113)
3. _____ FeCl₃ (HiMedia GRM1178)
4. _____ NH₄ClO₄ (Pyrochemsource)
5. _____ NaHCO₃ (Arm and Hammer)
6. _____ Distilled H₂O (DH₂O)
7. _____ Phenolphthalein (Innovating Science Product No. IS25036)

Safety:

We developed this protocol in a home laboratory. Whether using this protocol in a commercial/academic laboratory or a home-built laboratory, please follow all safety standards. Always wear gloves, eye protection and a lab coat. The reagents and resulting products of this protocol can be harmful if inhaled, ingested, or if they contact with skin. Remember to dispose of all resulting waste properly in accordance with legal and environmental protection requirements. Please perform this protocol under a proper ventilation fume hood, or outdoors as this protocol will produce harmful gasses including ammonia and hydrochloric acid. Reagents and products are flammable and can result in explosions if steps are skipped. Make sure that all proper fire prevention equipment is present. Please refer to the Illinois Division of Research Safety for more information on the safety considerations of handling perchloric acid (tmcgill).

Sodium Perchlorate Synthesis:

Balanced Equation

Note: Some excess NaOH will be added to ensure full reaction of the NH₄ClO₄

1. _____ In a 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask add 150 ml of DH₂O
2. _____ In a 50 ml Erlenmeyer Flask add 50 ml of DH₂O
3. _____ Add a magnetic stir bar to the 50 ml Erlenmeyer Flask and place on magnetic stirrer at medium speed
4. _____ Add 15.00 g (0.375 moles) of NaOH to a weight boat
5. _____ Add 15.00 g (0.375 moles) of NaOH to the 50 ml Erlenmeyer Flask and allow to dissolve
6. _____ Add a magnetic stir bar to the 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask and place on magnetic stirrer at medium speed
7. _____ Add 35.25 g (0.300 moles) of NH₄ClO₄ to a weight boat
8. _____ Add the 35.25 g (0.300 moles) of NH₄ClO₄ to the 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask and allow to dissolve
9. _____ Gradually add the NaOH solution in the 50 ml Erlenmeyer Flask to the solution of NH₄ClO₄ in the 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask

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10. _____ Allow to mix for 10 minutes
11. _____ Remove magnetic stir bar and add boiling stones
12. _____ Move the 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask to the hotplate and gradually bring the solution to a slow boil
13. _____ Once the 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask solution is boiling, test the fumes every 10 minutes with a pH strip by placing one drop of DH₂O on the strip and allowing it to soak into the strip. Then place the moist strip in the path of the exiting steam and fumes. The strip should indicate basic until all the NH_{3(g)} has left the solution
14. _____ Once the pH strip indicates neutral, turn off hot plate, and allow the solution to cool to room temperature

The resulting solution should be a solution of 0.300 moles of NaClO_{4(aq.)} with a concentration that will vary based on how much H₂O was boiled off.

Perchloric Acid Synthesis:

Balanced Equation

Note: The HCl volume will be an excess amount to ensure complete reaction of all basic compounds into salts. This excess will be boiled off.

1. _____ Clamp a 100 ml burette on a laboratory support stand
2. _____ Fill a 100 ml burette to the 67 ml line with HCl (A little over 33 ml)
3. _____ Place a magnetic stirrer underneath the burette
4. _____ Place the NaClO_{4(aq.)} solution 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask on the magnetic stirrer and turn on stirrer
5. _____ Add a stir bar to the 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask and stir at medium speed
6. _____ Open the burette so that the HCl drips slowly (approx. 1 drip/sec) into the 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask
7. _____ Once all the HCl has dripped into the solution, allow the reaction to occur for 10 minutes
8. _____ End Stirring and remove stir bar and allow the precipitants to settle
9. _____ Pour 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask with HClO_{4(aq.)} into a vacuum filtration and filter precipitated salts.
10. _____ Wash out 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask and place solution back in 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask
11. _____ Add Thermometer to beaker
12. _____ Add boiling stones to 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask
13. _____ Place 250 ml Erlenmeyer Flask with solution on a hot plate and bring the solution to a slow boil
14. _____ Observe the temperature reach between 105°C and 118°C

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15. _____ Once all the HCl excess and H₂O is evaporated the solution will steadily rise
16. _____ Once temperature reaches 130°C let boil for 10 more minutes then turn off hot plate and allow solution cool
17. _____ Observe that the solution will precipitate an excess amount of salts
18. _____ Once cooled, filter remaining salts out of solution
19. _____ Add purified solution to a 25 ml graduated cylinder and note the level

Perchloric Acid Concentration Confirmation:

1. _____ Add 25 ml of DH₂O to a 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask
2. _____ Add a stir bar to the flask and place on magnetic stirrer at medium stir
3. _____ Add 0.7 g of NaHCO₃ to the flask and stir until dissolved
4. _____ Place 25 ml burette onto lab stand
5. _____ Add the 25 ml NaHCO₃ solution to the burette
6. _____ Add 10 ml DH₂O to a clean 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask
7. _____ Add 1 ml of HClO₄(aq.) solution into the 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask
8. _____ Place Stir bar to 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask and place on a magnetic stirrer under the 25 ml burette, mix on medium
9. _____ Add 3 drops of phenolphthalein to the 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask
10. _____ Take note of the ml level on the 25 ml burette (L_s) = _____ ml
11. _____ Slowly drip NaHCO₃ solution into the 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask until the phenolphthalein indicates faint pink
12. _____ Note the level in the 25 ml burette (L_e) = _____ ml
13. _____ Take note of the volume of HClO₄(aq.) solution (V) = _____ ml
14. _____ Use equation 1 to calculate the amount moles present in the HClO₄(aq.) solution
15. _____ Use equation 2 to calculate the amount of DH₂O needed to bring HClO₄(aq.) solution to 35%.
16. _____ Transfer the HClO₄(aq.) solution to a 50 ml media bottle
17. _____ Add most of the amount of DH₂O required as calculated in equation 2 to the HClO₄(aq.) solution and reserve some to rinse the 25 ml graduated cylinder
18. _____ Add the reserve DH₂O to the 25 ml graduated cylinder and swirl around to dissolve remaining perchloric acid
19. _____ Add rest of DH₂O to the 50 ml media bottle
20. _____ Close 50 ml media bottle and vortex mix for 30 seconds.
21. _____ Label 50 ml media bottle “35% HClO₄(aq.) solution”
22. _____ Place media bottle in a refrigerator at below 40°C

Equation 1: $0.0006645(L_e - L_s) \times V = moles_{HClO_4} = \text{_____ moles}$

Equation 2: $\frac{moles_{HClO_4} \times 100.46}{1.67} \times \frac{13}{7} = V_{DH_2O} = \text{_____ ml}$

Ferric Chloride 0.5 M Solution Preparation

1. _____ Place a 150 ml beaker on a magnetic stirrer
2. _____ Add 50 ml of DH₂O to the 150 ml beaker
3. _____ Add a magnetic stir bar and stir at medium
4. _____ Weigh out and add 4.06 g of FeCl₃ to the 150 ml beaker
5. _____ Allow solution to dissolve
6. _____ Once dissolved, add solution to 50 ml media bottle and label "0.5 M FeCl₃"
7. _____ Place media bottle in a refrigerator at below 40°C

Salkowski Reagent Preparation:

Salkowski reagent is prepared by combining equal parts of the 0.5 M FeCl₃ solution and 35% HClO₄ solution at the desired volume based on need (Gang, Sharma and Saraf).

References

- Gang, Shraddha , et al. "Analysis of Indole-3-acetic Acid (IAA) Production in Klebsiellaby LC-MS/MS and the Salkowski Method." *Bio Protoc* (2019).
- Kamnev, A.A , et al. "Spectroscopic investigation of indole-3-acetic acid interaction with iron(III)." *Journal of Molecular Structure* (2001): 565-572.
- tmcgill. *Illinois Division of Research Safety*. 24 4 2014. Website. 16 4 2022.
<<https://drs.illinois.edu/Page/SafetyLibrary/PerchloricAcid>>.